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CHINA RUTH ASIS-LIBRADO

**“All we need is love”: The Influence of Humanized
Communication to Selected Adult Quezon City Residents in
Adopting Preventive Measures against COVID-19**

Thesis Adviser:

ALEXANDER G. FLOR
Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

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Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by **CHINA RUTH ASIS-LIBRADO** with the title: “ ‘**ALL WE NEED IS LOVE**’: **THE INFLUENCE OF HUMANIZED COMMUNICATION TO SELECTED ADULT QUEZON CITY RESIDENTS IN ADOPTING PREVENTIVE MEASURES AGAINST COVID-19**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Program.

Dr. Alexander G. Flor
Chair, Thesis Committee

September 8, 2023

Dr. Melinda DP. Bandalaria
Member, Thesis Committee

September 8, 2023

Dr. Benjamina Paula G. Flor
Member, Thesis Committee

September 8, 2023

Diego S. Maranan, Ph.D.

Dean

Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

23 August 2023

Biographical Sketch

The author, China Ruth Asis-Librado, was born in 1990 in the city of Mandaluyong, Philippines. Since she was a little, she was fond of watching documentaries and dreamt of taking a Media related course. To pursue her interest, she took Bachelor of Arts in Communication Arts at Philippine Women's University.

When she graduated in 2014, she started teaching at La Verdad Christian College in Caloocan and was able to share her passion to aspiring Broadcast and Communication practitioners in the said institution which offers 100% free education to poor yet deserving Filipino students.

To further improve her pedagogical skills in teaching, she took 18-units of educational program and was able to pass the Licensure for Professional Teacher in 2022.

Though she never imagined being a teacher, she found her purpose in teaching and realized this is her way of fulfilling the duty of agent of change. Anchored in the teachings of her dearest Ingkong and Kuya, she grew up with the lessons they have taught her saying: "Do not withhold doing good to whom it is due when the power of doing so is in your hands."

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Dedicated to:

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Kuya Daniel Razon

Christian Librado

Nancy Muros-Asis

Fernando Asis

Fernando Asis Jr.

Chabilita & Aya

Sasha & Tazkie

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Abstract

“ALL WE NEED IS LOVE”: THE INFLUENCE OF HUMANIZED COMMUNICATION TO SELECTED ADULT QUEZON CITY RESIDENTS IN ADOPTING PREVENTIVE MEASURES AGAINST COVID-19

There are numerous ways to influence and motivate people to action. In the Philippines, public compliance to COVID-19 preventive measures has become quite challenging. Reports showed in 2021 that thousands of quarantine violators were recorded by the PNP. Medical health experts have proven that layers of protection such as vaccination, face masks, eye protection (using face shields), physical distancing, minimizes the risk of contracting the virus. Thus, it is significant to carefully consider the communication strategy that should be employed to motivate the public to adopt the changes brought by the “new normal” era because of the COVID-19. In this study, the researcher employed theory of reasoned action to determine what motivates the public’s intention to adopt the preventive measures against COVID-19. According to its proponents, there are two variables that influence the intention of an individual to adopt a behavior; the attitude towards behavior and the subjective norm. It is said that the higher positive attitude towards a behavior and subjective norm a person has, the intention to adopt the behavior is more likely to happen. Hence, the researcher introduced in this study “humanized communication” as a factor that also influences positively the intention of an individual to adopt the said behavior. Humanized communication refers to the use of exceptional storytelling that enhances persuasive messages by touching emotions and moving people to favorable response. Thus, humanized communication through storytelling was measured through the

following variables; (1) If it touches EMOTION, (2) If it evokes EMPATHY, and (3) if it inspires ACTION.

The study collected and analyzed data from 278 adult respondents from Quezon City. To measure the association between the factors of humanized communication and preventive measures compliance against COVID-19, the Spearman's rank correlation test was used. Furthermore, Cronbach's Alpha was employed to measure the reliability of the test.

Results showed that the ad campaign which uses a humanize communication strategy through storytelling that was able to tap emotion, evokes empathy and inspire action has a positive correlation to influence the individual's intention to adopt the preventive measures against COVID-19. Hence, health communication experts may consider humanized communication through storytelling technique as a factor that can be maximized in crafting effective health advertisement campaign.

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Messages are considered the very core of communication study. As one of the crucial components of communication, it is designed to stimulate response to its receiver. According to Griffin (2011), if a message fails to elicit any cognitive, emotional, or behavioral response, communication theorists concluded that it is pointless to consider it as communication. When a receiver attaches the same meaning to the word provided by the sender, communication on its real essence happens. Primarily, the term communication came from the Greek word “*communicare*” which means, “commonness.” Thus, creating a connection between the speaker and the listener is necessary for effective communication (Maslog, 2010).

Communication experts in Marketing and Advertising realized that one way to establish connections to people to elicit a desired response from the identified target audience is by humanizing communication through stories. Humanized communication through storytelling was said to be one of the best business tools in influencing behavior of your target audience considering that through stories, it connects you and your target audience to the “emotional why” of the message you would like to convey (Belt, 2023).

In response to the developmental works in the country, this research seeks to introduce and prove that by humanizing communication through storytelling, it influences the compliance of the selected adult Quezon City residents to the preventive measures against COVID-19. Using the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)

which shows the determining factors of an individual if it will conduct or not a behavior (Yzer, 2012), the study aimed to show how humanizing communication through storytelling that elicits emotion, evokes empathy, and persuasiveness to inspire action, are factors that may influence their intention to comply to the basic health protocols in preventing the spread of the virus- the desired communication response.

As early as 1977, the idea of humanizing data was already employed by astrophysicist Neil deGrasse Tyson for science communication to help them effectively educate the people about the NASA Cassini space probe to explore Saturn. By humanizing data, they turn the data into language humans can understand. Tyson considered it as a secret to science communication whenever you humanize data in a way you present it in an interesting, engaging, memorable and persuasive way, making it relevant to the receivers of your message (Gallo, 2022).

In brand communication, exceptional storytelling is humanized storytelling (Emmerson, 2021). The power of storytelling enhances persuasive messages by touching the emotions and moving the consumer to favorable responses (Moriarty et al., 2014). The extraordinary brand storytelling always strikes an emotional chord (Emmerson, 2021).

The power of visual storytelling enhances the impact of the message we would like to convey to our audience. With videos as a component of visual storytelling, it has a compelling characteristic that makes it personal, it draws attention and it resonates with viewers in a way other mediums cannot (Walter & Gioglio, 2014).

In industries such as Advertising, effective communication materials create impact. Facets of impact namely: Perception, Emotion/affect, Cognition, Association,

Persuasion, and Behavior are the six effects- model proposed by Moriarty et al., deemed to be useful in setting advertising material's objectives and evaluating the effectiveness of an advertising material (Moriarty et al., 2014). According to Velasco et al., (1999), the government is utilizing social marketing and social mobilization to promote development in our country.

Maslow's hierarchy of needs mentioned that the social needs that motivate human behavior include love. The need for emotional relationships drives the behavior of an individual (Cherry, 2022). The involvement and the sense of connectedness we get from our personal relationships with friends, family and even in our community are part of the human emotional need that drives a person's behavior to do something (Mcleod, 2023).

In the perspective of development communication, our motivation as an agent of change is the need to communicate change to transform lives (Quebral, 2012). Society needs change. "Development is social change for the better and communication plays a central role in social development" (Flor, 2003). A perspective coming from a professor and a scientist but at the same time, a parent, and a father of four who sees in the eyes of every child he meets the eyes of his own child.

Hence, the researcher recognized the need to formulate humanized communication materials in addressing developmental issues in the country.

Statement of the Problem

1. What is humanized communication?
2. What are the factors that humanize communication?

3. How humanizing communication influences preventive measures' compliance against COVID-19 among QC residents?

Objectives of the Study

1. To define and explore what humanizes communication?
2. To enumerate the factors that humanize communication.
3. To explain how the factors of humanized communication influence preventive measure's compliance against COVID-19 among QC residents.

Hypotheses of the Study

There is a relationship between humanized communication in influencing the intention of the selected adult QC residents to adopt preventive measures against COVID-19.

Significance of the Study

This study will help development communicators deployed in different sectors in our society, from the LGU and private sectors, which author social mobilization campaigns in raising effective awareness campaigns in fighting epidemic diseases such as COVID-19.

The findings of this study will be a valuable reference to development communication practitioners utilizing the media for information dissemination as it will

provide how the phenomena of humanizing communication in the digital age can be a game-changer in mobilizing the public.

This study will benefit those development communication practitioners who practice as advisers to policy makers in communicating public health policies in preventing the diffusion of epidemic diseases such as the Novel CoronaVirus.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study was demarcated on assessing the influence of humanized communication towards selected adult Quezon City residents regarding their compliance with the preventive measures amidst the fight against COVID-19. Accordingly, it has been reported that Quezon City has the leading COVID-19 positive cases among all the cities in the National Capital Region with 277,000 as of May 2023. Due to restrictions and safety in collecting the data, survey questionnaires were distributed online to identified Quezon City residents ages 18 and above.

Operational Definition of Terms

The following terms used in the study were operationally defined for the guidance of the readers:

Humanized Communication is an independent variable introduced by a researcher that influences the intention of an individual to perform a behavior. Humanized communication through storytelling has the following components in which it affects

the intention of an individual to perform the desired behavior: It taps EMOTION, it evokes EMPATHY, and it inspires ACTION. The researcher chose an advertisement campaign from P&G Philippines entitled, “A Frontliner’s Sacrifice,” as an example of a humanized communication material, and has asked the respondents to watch the material before answering the questionnaire.

For this study’s purpose, it aimed to figure out whether humanized communication influences compliance with preventive measures against COVID-19. This was measured using the Likert’s Scale (Strongly agree to strongly disagree) with the respondents answering five questions:

HC-1. Ang ad campaign ay epektibo sa pagkuha ng interes ng tao para sumunod sa mga kalimitang paraan para maiiwasan ang pagkalat ng COVID-19 katulad ng pagsunod sa Social distancing, pag-isolate, pagsusuot ng facemask, at pagpapabakuna.

HC- 2. Nakuha ang iyong interest ng bidyo dahil ito ay nakapaghatid ng mensahe na sa pagsunod natin sa mga health protocols para mapigilan ang pagkalat ng COVID-19 ay magliligtas ng buhay ng lahat, lalo't higit ng ating sariling pamilya at mga mahal sa buhay.

HC-3. Sa pagpapakita ng totoong kwento ng buhay ng mga frontliners katulad ng pangangailangang malayo sa pamilya at mahal sa buhay ay nagbigay motibasyon sa iyo upang gawin ang iyong parte upang mapigil ang pagkalat ng sakit na COVID-19.

HC-4. Ang ad campaign ay higit na nakakahimok dahil ito ay nakapagpakita ng reyalidad ng buhay ng mga frontliners tulad ng mga nurse, doktor, medical personnel,

pulis, delivery riders, etc, sa panahon ng pandemic kumpara sa sakripisyo ng majority ng mga Pilipino na kailangan manatili sa bahay habang pinairal ang mga lockdown.

HC-5. Ang pagbibigay diin sa kwento ng sakripisyo ng mga frontliners sa ad campaign video ay sumasalamin sa resulta ng di pagsunod ng iba sa mga health protocols laban sa COVID-19. Ito ay nagbigay sayo ng sapat na dahilan para makiisa at sumunod sa health protocols.

Evokes Emotion is one of the components of humanized communication. For this study's purpose, the identified drivers of emotion are the material's ability to arouse interest/attention and memorability of the content to the audience. This was measured using the Likert Scale (Strongly agree to strongly disagree) with the respondents answering six questions:

EMO-1. Ang paraan ng pagkukuwento sa Ad campaign ay nakukuha ang attention ng manonood.

EMO-2. Ang ad campaign sa paglaban sa COVID-19 ay nakakapukaw ng interes dahil sa paraan ng pagkukuwento na binigyang diin ang pagpapakita ng sakripisyo at paghihirap na dinadanas ng mga frontliners.

EMO-3. Napukaw ang iyong interest sa video dahil nakasalalay din ang buhay at kapalaran ng mga frontliners at ng kanilang pamilya sa pagsunod natin sa mga health protocols.

EMO-4. Ang ad campaign ay nagbigay ng malinaw na larawan sa naranasang paghihirap at sakripisyo ng mga frontliners para lang magampanan ang kanilang mga tungkulin.

EMO-5. Ang kwento ng pagsasakripisyo at paghihirap ng mga frontliners ay nagpapaalala sayo ng kahalagahan ng pag-oobserba ng health protocols laban sa COVID-19.

EMO-6. Kahit walang salita patungkol sa health protocols para mapigil ang pagkalat ng COVID-19, ang mensahe ay epektibong naihatid sa pamamagitan ng malinaw na larawan ng kwento patungkol sa pang araw-araw na sakripisyo at hirap ng mga frontliners.

Evokes Empathy is one of the components of humanized communication. For the purpose of this study, the identified drivers of empathy is the ability of the material to resonate with the audience. This was measured using the Likert Scale (Strongly agree to strongly disagree) with the respondents answering two questions:

EMP-1. Ang pagpapakita ng totoong buhay ng ating frontliners na pinakita sa ad campaign ay nakatulong sayo ma-realize paano ka at ang iyong mga mahal sa buhay makikinabang mula sa pagsunod sa mga health protocols laban sa COVID-19.

EMP-2. Para sayo, gusto mo ba na irekomendang makakita ng mas maraming katulad nito na video dahil sa iyong palagay, ito ay epektibo na napapaunawa ang sitwasyon tungkol sa COVID-19?

Elicit Action is one of the components of humanized communication. For this study's purpose, the identified driver of action is the persuasiveness of the material to the audience. This was measured using the Likert Scale (Extremely likely to Extremely unlikely) with the respondents answering four questions:

A-1. Gaano ang posibilidad na susundin mo ang health protocols laban sa COVID-19 matapos makita ang kwento ng sakripisyo ng ating mga frontliners?

A-2. Gaano ang posibilidad na ibabahagi mo ang ad campaign na tulad nito na tumutukoy sa kwento ng totoong buhay ng frontliners para makatulong sa pagpapalaganap ng kamalayan para mapigil ang pagkalat ng COVID-19?

A-3. Sa iyong palagay, gaano ang posibilidad na maisip ng tao ang pangangailangan na sumunod sa health protocols laban sa COVID-19 pagkatapos makapanood ng mga kwento gaya ng pinakita sa ad campaign.

A-4. Gaano ang posibilidad na ikaw ay sumunod sa health protocols laban sa COVID-19 matapos makita ang malalang epekto nito sa buhay ng mga frontliners at ng kanilang mga mahal sa buhay?

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

What is communication and what is humanized communication?

In Em Griffin's working definition of the term communication, she mentioned that "Communication is the relational process of creating and interpreting messages that elicit a response." Notably, the communication's final component from the definition reiterated the significance of messages that elicit response. Thus, it is pointless to say that it is communication without the message stimulating any cognitive, emotional, or behavioral reaction (Griffin, 2011).

Additionally, just as breathing should not be taken for granted, neither should the notion that writing or speaking constitutes communication. Maslog (2010) emphasized that real communication happens only when someone listens, and when the sender and the receiver of a message attach the same meanings to the word use. The etymology of the term communication in Greek is "communicare, which means "commonness." Thus, establishing a connection between the speaker and the listener becomes necessary when talking about communication (Maslog, 2010).

Reiterating the importance of establishing connection to people to elicit response, Belt (2023) expounded that stories can humanize and connect people in ways that facts and figures cannot. Simply because, stories connect you and your target audience to the "emotional why" of the message you would like to convey. Stories are "the currency of human connection" (McKee, 2018). Through storytelling,

we can connect to people, thus communicating with them, making it one of the best business tools in influencing our audience's behavior (Belt, 2023); thus, to elicit a response. Storytelling is a humanized communication as stories connect us. Hence, establishing connection to people through stories is communication.

In science communication, you must humanize data to create value to people. Having any data point interesting by placing the number in perspective is humanizing it, a trick in reducing the cognitive load in communication science (Gallo, 2022).

In advertising, effective visual storytelling is telling interesting stories that are engaging and maintain interest (Moriarty et al., 2014). Business experts now concur that humanizing content through tales is a sure-fire approach to leave a lasting impression on your audience because it helps people connect and learn more than other mediums. Furthermore, the need for employing the art of storytelling is deemed to be the way to humanize content, it becomes necessary for businesses to reconnect with its potential audiences (Zimmatore, 2021).

What are the factors that humanize communication?

Discussing how great leaders communicate, Gallo (2022) wrote the significance of humanizing data to create value to people. He shared Neil deGrasse Tyson's secret to science communication emphasizing that one of the secrets to science communication is to "embed the concept in familiar ground" by means of turning data into language that humans can understand.

As an example of humanizing data, in 1977, astrophysicist Tyson was able to provide a data comparison by being rhetorically creative when he guested in a

television show to educate the people about the benefits of the NASA Cassini space probe to explore Saturn.

As the mission's price tag was \$3 billion, he said, "Americans spend more on lip balm every year than NASA would spend on the said mission". Hence, instead of introducing the data in plain numbers, making it interesting is humanizing the data. It is an extra step we make if we present it in an engaging, memorable, and persuasive way. Have the data relevant to the listeners and that is how you humanize data (Gallo, 2022).

Emphasizing the power of visual storytelling, messages can be even more powerful when they are accompanied by visuals. A beautiful and impactful story with simple graphics can help establish deeper understanding and connection with the message. More so, the power of videos is evident to companies which help them connect to enormous size of audience for the following compelling characteristics of videos; personal, draws attention and resonate with viewers in a way other mediums cannot. But no matter how well a video is produced, the audience will not watch or share the content if the information is not valuable to them (Walter & Gioglio (2014).

To connect with the customers on a deeper level, aligning the video goals to the audience's needs is the key. In the case of Dove's "Real Beauty Sketches campaign," the company used a video to communicate an inspirational mission that encourages confidence in women and feeling beautiful is powerful. As it was able to make the audience realize that they are more beautiful than what they think, today, the video has 70 million views and counting (Walter & Gioglio, 2014).

Even in brand communication, exceptional storytelling is humanized storytelling (Emmerson, 2021). The power of storytelling enhances persuasive messages by touching the emotions and moving the consumer to favorable response (Moriarty et al., 2014).

The extraordinary brand storytelling always strikes an emotional chord. Good storytelling creates empathy. As a brand, you understand your audience's realities and challenges. Offering help by providing a solution shows you care about your consumer. Thus, humanized storytelling has a quality that touches emotions of people through stories that does not only ring true but honest (Emmerson, 2021). In many situations concerning advertising, it is said that "emotion is the key driver of a prospect being 'turned on' to a message" (Moriarty et al., 2014).

In principles of advertising, the use of visuals is way more effective than words. It is better in grabbing and keeping people's attention. As visuals persist in the mind, the message tends to stick to the audience's memory. Effective use of visuals cement belief as visuals helps provide credibility to a message presented. Inevitably, it communicates quickly as picture communicates instantly, helping your audience to easily digest your message. Lastly, employing visual storytelling by giving an interesting story to the audience that is engaging and maintains interest of the public makes it significant in persuading people to move into action (Moriarty et al., 2014).

Effective communication materials in advertising create impact. Facets of impact namely: Perception, Emotion/affect, Cognition, Association, Persuasion, and Behavior are the six effects-model proposed by Moriarty et al., deemed to be useful in setting advertising material's objectives and evaluating the effectiveness of an advertising material (Moriarty et al., 2014).

The need to call for preventive measures against COVID-19

As of March 12, 2022, the Department of Health recorded almost 453-million confirmed cases worldwide of the newly discovered disease, the Novel Coronavirus or commonly known as COVID-19. In just two years, our country has documented nearly 3.7 million cases.

According to the World Health Organization's (WHO) research, they emphasized that chances for mutation of the virus increases when we give it an opportunity to circulate (WHO, 2021). For this reason, the Department of Health (D.O.H.) suggested isolation protocols for people considered suspect, probable, or confirmed positive for COVID-19.

Verily, medical authorities reiterated that there are numerous undocumented COVID-19 cases that can no longer be traced by health authorities. Report says, possibilities of spreading further the virus are caused by asymptomatic individuals with mild symptoms who are not aware they already have the virus resulting in unintentional spread of the virus. (bioMerieux Connection Editors, 2021). Moreover, medical experts advised these asymptomatic persons to better monitor themselves and isolate themselves immediately especially if you are experiencing symptoms of the virus. (Isolation, 2022). Based on several studies conducted, the virus mutates and evolves as the virus reaches many people. Thus, preventing the spread of the virus is a proactive move in order to stop the virus' mutation (Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19): Variants of SARS-COV-2, n.d.)

In relation to this, we can recall that back in late December of 2021 to January of 2022, the overwhelming surge of positive cases of COVID-19 occurred in the country.

Various drugstores in Metro Manila went out of stock of basic medicines to fight cough and flu such as Paracetamol. The phenomenon of omicron variant explains why mutation of the virus is a perilous scenario to see. Noticeably, this happened during the time of relaxed public health measures where it is no longer mandatory to wear face masks and face shields in public places, social distancing is no longer being practiced especially in public utility transportation (WHO, 2022).

Quarantining, Isolation, Social Distancing and Wearing of Face Masks: A problematic issue among Filipinos

After more than two years, the downward trend of COVID-19 cases in the Philippines started to be felt in several places in the country as reported in October 2022. As per the OCTA Research Group, a significant decrease in the number of new positive cases was recorded in the National Capital Region with fewer than 500 positive cases in 7 days. The positivity rate was described to have 11.6% from 14.6% (CNN, 2022). This progress was followed by a declaration from President Marcos Jr. allowing voluntary wearing of face masks (Frasco, 2022). However, in just seven months, the number of positive cases in the country has started to pick up again with average daily cases up by 112% from May 1-8 of 2023 (Manila Bulletin, 2023).

In some reports, quarantining and isolation are one of the most taken for granted health measures in the country. In fact, during the All-Saint's Day celebration in the country back in 2021, the Philippine National Police (PNP) listed 48,000 quarantine protocol violators in the entire country. Moreover, there are 101,000 curfew violators and almost 40,000 non-authorized persons found outside their residence (Mendoza, 2021).

Back in 2022, quarantining protocols to those who came from outside the country including the United States of America was still being implemented in the entire country. The day after the New Year's eve of 2022, a report circulated about a Filipino woman who came from the USA and faced raps for partying and violating the quarantine protocol. Unfortunately, the woman was found to be positive for COVID-19 including 15 of whom she was with (Santos, 2022).

Observing how some people takes for granted how the mandated health protocols such as quarantining would help us control the further spread of the virus, the story of "Poblacion Girl" who went out to party despite of being mandated to undergo quarantine prompted Senator Juan Miguel Zubiri to amend Republic Act 11332. The honorable senator suggested implementing higher penalties for those who will be guilty for violating quarantine protocols (Ramos, 2022).

To mollify the situation of COVID-19 in the country, the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) was established. They are responsible for providing general instructions to be implemented in the entire local government units for uniform response in containing the virus. The agency is considering the possibility that quarantining will stop the virus from spreading, but it also considers that a complete economic collapse would be a nightmare for everyone who needs to support their families, including the government.

Similarly, wearing face masks, especially in public transport and other confined establishments, has contributed to the continued low case rates of COVID-19 in the country even as mobility normalized. According to Dr. Edsel Salvana, while it is true that no intervention is 100% effective, vaccination, ventilation, face masks, eye protection (using face shields), and physical distancing was proven to decrease the risk of COVID-19. These protection layers were successful in minimizing the risk of

contracting the contagious virus. Thus, even if there is a breakthrough infection, this will tend to be mild since the amount of virus that gets through is substantially decreased (Dr. Salvana, 2023).

HOW COVID-19 Affects the Lives of Filipinos

Definitely, COVID-19 has brought many losses to Filipino households in many forms. Jobs were taken, our entire lives were changed. In 2021, the World Bank conducted a survey to demonstrate the real impact of the virus on the economy that can be mirrored at the level of Filipino families (WB, 2021).

It has been recorded on the World Bank's survey that Filipino families with low-income were the ones deeply affected by the COVID-19. From 73% of Filipino children who were able to pay visit in health centers, it went down to 41% during the lockdown (WB, 2020).

In a published document by the World Bank about the impacts of COVID-19 on communities in the Philippines, the result shows that in terms of social safety nets, it has been said that the communities preferred food, cash, and livelihood assistance. It can be noted that the survey was conducted in April 2021 where all Barangay in the country was in MGCQ or Modified General Community Quarantine. During MGCQ, all private offices are allowed to operate anywhere between fifty percent to 100% on-site capacity. However, establishments like entertainment venues (karaoke bars, bars, clubs, concert halls, theaters, amusement industries, cockfighting) are still prohibited to operate during MGCQ (Department of Health, 2021).

In relation to this, the economic effect assessment reveals that for the majority of people, a lack of income was the biggest issue, and many cited reduced or lost

employment possibilities. The worst hit by employment cuts and job losses were our construction workers and public transportation drivers, which bothered men and women equally. (World Bank, 2021).

Visiting how the community perceived the government's services during the pandemic, the survey reported that for the community, the local government could do better in implementing health protocols (World Bank, 2021).

According to Giamarinaro (2020), the pandemic that resulted to loss of income to many Filipino households brought them to unfortunate situations to survive especially to vulnerable individuals. Victims of trafficking and exploitation increased, as the pandemic pushed millions people to extreme poverty.

The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) emphasized due to pandemic-related measures many of the NGOs working with the said organization lose their means of income and access to food staples. In some cases, loan sharks make low-interest loan promises that could lead to debt-bondage. As they look for ways to guarantee their livelihoods with them, the possibility of severe exploitation has increased. UNODC noted that "people are trafficked for many exploitative purposes such as forced labor, child soldiers, forced begging, sexual exploitation, forced marriage, selling children and even removal of organs" (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2021).

Social Interventions, Social mobilization, and Public Compliance

Choon Chekkar, Joshua Moon, and Michael Hopkins (2021) emphasized on their article published by The Conversation that South Korea's formula for a success policy response is "a combination of high technology with a human touch," making

South Korea's pandemic response admired by the world for being exceptional. The so called "social interventions" in taking care of their people resulted to positive compliance of their countrymen with its isolation policy.

True enough, human intervention was seen working and has been effective in South Korea in preventing further spread of the virus. Meaning, once a positive case is detected, human intervention is being practiced. Thus, being able to get the public's cooperation with the government policy was a big contributory factor on the success of their campaign to fight COVID-19 (Chekkar et al., 2021). A study written by Olivier Bargain entitled "Trust and Compliance to Public Health Policies in Times of COVID-19" highlighted that trust and cohesion within a country is often shown to have large socioeconomic impacts M(Bargain, 2020).

Professor Crispin Maslog on his book entitled, "Philippine Communication Today", reiterated that;

"The government can only succeed only to the extent that they are supported by their people. The support of people can be won either by persuasion or coercion, or both."

Bargain's research wrote that it aims to find out whether the compliance to these containment policies depends on the level of trust in policy makers prior to the crisis.

In Bargain's research, he used the difference-in-differences method, a quasi-experimental approach that compares changes in outcomes overtime (DIME Wiki). The results indicate that regions with high trust significantly reduce mobility compared

to regions with low trust and, on average, tend to comply with policy stringency more. This was done to figure out whether the trust effect has anything to do with the public's compliance with public health policies even when they are stringent. (Bargain, 2020).

Meanwhile, Sofie Marein and Marc Hooghe (2021) gave an assumption on their research entitled, "Does political trust matter? An Empirical investigation into the relation between political trust and support for law compliance," that if a government receives low level of trust, it will find it more acceptable to break the law.

Furthermore, it states that with low levels of political trust, the effectiveness and legitimacy of government actions and its ability to implement legislation is compromised, implying that the two is correlated in seeing positive response from its people (Mareine & Hogghe, 2011).

In addition, the study of Antok Pak, Emma McBryde, and Oyelola Adegboye in 2021 that talks about whether public trust amplifies compliance if stringent COVID-19 health guidelines were implemented by the government, outlined that as the government stays true to its public, the result showed that it doubled the impact of public compliance despite of policy restrictions. Meaning, earned public trust despite strict policy and compliance is correlated for having a positive behavior of the public (Pak et al., 2021).

In 2015, West Africa experienced the largest Ebola Outbreak recorded in their region. In response to this epidemic disease, experts have found that community engagement helped significantly to contain the said outbreak. Through social mobilization efforts, community leaders have proven that prevention has been the best strategy to employ and that includes promoting eagerly the basic health protocols to

their constituents such as self-imposed quarantine, surveillance, hygiene and including proper management of burials (Laverack & Mannoncourt, 2016).

Furthermore, extending help to those people needed to be quarantined was seen to have positive reception among its people in Liberia during the surge of Ebola to cooperate and adopt the health policy. Understanding their situation during their isolation helped lessen quarantine violators in their region. Thus, community leaders continued to provide essentials such as water, food, money and most importantly, equipped them with information on what to do when one contracted the said disease. Indeed, the result showed that most of the community who displayed cooperation to contain the Ebola virus was influenced by social intervention initiated by their community leaders.

On the contrary, the study has determined that coercion is a counterproductive activity of the latter's discussion. It was seen that "large-scale forced quarantine" in Liberia had negative repercussions as it defeats the goals of community engagement which is to win their cooperation (Laverack & Mannoncourt, 2016). This reminds us of a similar situation we have seen in our country where strict lockdown for months still resulted in thousands of quarantine and curfew violators.

According to the study of Laverack et al., (2016), cultural issues can be a factor to influence people to comply with the health policy to control the Ebola outbreak in Africa. For instance, in communities like Liberia, one must consider that deep-seated practices within the community exist. Transmission of the Ebola persisted due to continued hiding of sick people including dead bodies, and practicing unsafe burial. Thus, engaging people for dialogue is a must in this kind of situation. However, the investigation showed that the outbreak progressed as the Ebola response was slow

to adapt a more targeted approach in this kind of community. Evidently, understanding the context of our audience before communicating is significant for a successful communication (Laverack et al., 2016).

In addition, the investigation shows that the unwillingness of the people to change the traditional practices constituted by the lack of support for quarantined families and patients and this has been chaotic to the community itself. It eventually developed an atmosphere of mistrust, fear, resistance, and non-compliance to the Ebola response in Africa. Hence, building a narrative of trust through communication is difficult; ideally, community confidence should be maintained from the beginning through bottom-up approaches that include a respect for local perspectives (Laverack et al., 2016).

Regarding the concept discussed above, Kaiser (2012) articulated that the bottom-up approach emphasizing local community participation in development initiatives is possible if it enables them to determine their own objectives and means of achieving them.

Studies using Theory of Reasoned Action

The researcher used the theory of reasoned action (TRA) by Martin Fishbein and Icek Ajzen. The key concept of TRA according to its proponents will help you understand the “actual behavior of an individual by tracing the behavioral intention of the subject”. Experts emphasized that it is used as a reliable tool to predict actual behavior of your determined audience. Using this theory, we examine the attitude and the expectations of people or what we refer to as subjective norms to determine and predict the behavioral intent of an individual.

In Roghayed Ezari Rad et al. (2022), they employed theory of reasoned action as the best predictor to determine “the COVID-19 vaccine intention of people from South of Iran”. The researchers believed that by identifying the relevant and predictive beliefs of South Iran regarding COVID-19 vaccine, this will help craft an effective health interventions promotion about the vaccination to address hesitancy to take the vaccine and increase the number of people who will take the vaccine. Cross-sectional study was utilized from May 2021 to July 2021 through a web-based self-administered questionnaire in South Iran that includes 18 years of age and above.

Xiao (2019) used TRA to investigate and determine “the factors that correspond to behavioral intentions of watching eSports in the U.S. by adopting structural equation modeling analysis”. This helped the researcher to see the relationship between intentions of the public in watching eSports, their attitude, including the subjective norms, behavioral and normative beliefs. The result shows subjective norms and behavioral beliefs that include aesthetics, drama, and escapism, were related to the attitude toward watching eSports. Data was collected through an online survey (MTurk) with 295 respondents, not more than 60 years of age.

Dawi et al. (2021) studied “the determinants of intention to observe preventive behavior as key to reducing the spread of COVID-19 virus”. The researchers describe how the public's perception of the information and services given by the e-government affects their attitude in participation in preventive behavior programs in Malaysia using a cross sectional online survey with 400 valid responses in Malaysia. The result shows favorable importance in using digital platforms today to improve people's attitude toward preventive behavior to help contain the spread of the virus.

Xuewei & Hongliang Chen (2020) examined using TRA “the difference of adopting preventive behaviors of COVID-19 between urban and rural residents in China”. In their study, they utilized multiple linear regressions and path analysis for comparing data between rural and urban respondents with 1,591 responses from a total of 31 provinces in China. The result shows that compared to urban residents, people in rural areas were found to be less likely to adopt preventive measures against COVID-19. The study suggests that rural residents have identified unique needs that suggest the importance of tailoring health messages appropriate to rural population’s needs for them to be able to engage in adopting the preventive measures against the virus.

A similar study was conducted in South Iran by Moghadam et al. (2022). In their research, they focused on the youth adults in rural areas of South Iran, investigating the factors that affect and influence their adoption to preventive measures to contain the transmission of COVID-19. Cross-sectional survey was also used to collect data utilizing online questionnaires. 304 youth in rural areas of South Iran participated in a survey through a random sampling technique (18-30 years of age). Based on the study’s result, it is evident that understanding the benefits of adopting preventive behavior among youth adults significantly affects their participation in the said health measure. Significant number of respondents were more likely to adopt the behavior who understands that the recommended behaviors like home quarantine and use of safeguards may help prevent the COVID-19 infection. It implies that understanding the benefits drives most of the respondents to engage in preventive measures against the virus.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

For the study's purpose, the researcher incorporated the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) conceptualized by Martin Fishbein and Icek Ajzen in 1975.

Figure 1. *Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) by Martin Fishbein and Icek Ajzen, 1975*

TRA aims to explain one's behavior by "identifying primary determinants of behavior and the sources of these determinant variables and by organizing the relations between these variables" (Yzer, 2012). The three principle constructs that determine an individual's behavior are the (1) intention, (2) subjective norms and the (3) attitude toward a behavior.

The theory proposes that the most important determining factor if an individual will or will not conduct a behavior is its intention. It is said that the greater the intention of an individual, the greater likelihood of performing a behavior. Individual's intentions are influenced by two factors. It relates the attitude toward behavior and the sense of subjective norm.

Attitude refers to a person's positive or negative thoughts concerning the performance of a behavior. Attitude is influenced by two factors; an individual's beliefs about the consequences of doing a specific behavior and the evaluation of those consequences.

Subjective norm refers to how much pressure a person feels to perform a particular action. Influenced by two factors as well; the individual's perception about the expectations of other people and the motivation to comply with these perceived expectations. For half a century, the theory of reasoned action served as a foundation for persuasion research (Yzer, 2012).

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 2. *Conceptual Framework of the Study*

The original model has two independent variables affecting the intention of an individual to adopt a behavior, namely; Attitude and Subjective norms. It must be noted that the researcher introduced and added humanized communication as an

independent variable to the model that affects the intention of an individual to adopt a behavior.

Humanized communication refers to exceptional storytelling (Emmerson, 2021). It is said that it enhances persuasive messages by touching emotions and moving people to favorable response (Moriarty et al., 2014). Thus, the positive impact of humanized communication which refers to the compliance to the preventive measures' against COVID-19 will be measured through the following variables: (1) If it touches **EMOTION**, (2) If it evokes **EMPATHY**, and (3) if it inspires **ACTION**.

In principles of advertising, emotion refers to a hook that helps engage the attention and contributes to the depth of the memory traces left behind by a brand message. Hence, this will be measured by the following factors considered to be one of the drivers of emotion; if the material draws **INTEREST/ATTENTION** and if the material is **MEMORABLE** to a person (Moriarty et al., 2014).

Good storytelling creates empathy. Thus, it understands your audience's realities and challenges (Emmerson, 2021). Ads that emphasize the emotional impact of a message by engaging in a personal connection with a brand's message are said to resonate with the target audience (Moriarty et al., 2014). To measure if the humanized communication material evokes empathy, it will be measured by checking if the material **RESONATES/ ENGAGING** with the audience.

The last variable is about seeing if the humanized communication material inspires action. For this study, the researcher would like to present whether a humanized communication material positively affects or influences the intention of an individual. Relatively, it influences the likelihood of adopting a behavior. Persuasion is

all about influencing or motivating the receiver of a message to believe or do something. Hence, persuasive communication intends to create or change attitudes and conviction (Moriarty et al., 2014). To measure if humanized communication drives people to action, it will be measuring if the material is **PERSUASIVE** to the audience to elicit a positive response, in which, the compliance to the preventive measures against COVID-19.

Humanized communication through storytelling, with the observable characteristics of tapping the emotion, evoking empathy, and inspiring people to move to action, thus, positively influences attitude and the subjective norm- giving an individual a greater intention and greater likelihood to perform a behavior.

CHAPTER III

METHODOLOGY

Research design

For the purpose of this study, the researcher employed a quantitative approach. This approach according to Bouchrika (2023) is said to be best suited for a research goal where actionable insight is tied to a statistical conclusion.

This research employed a one-time survey, the most basic research design according to Campbell & Stanley (1959) in which a single group is studied only once, after some agent or treatment presumed to cause change. A survey is “the collection of information from a sample of individuals through their responses to questions” (Check & Schutt, 2012).

Local of the study

This study focused on selected adult Quezon City residents. It has been reported that Quezon City had the highest number of COVID-19 cases among all the cities in the National Capital Region from 2020 up to May 2023 with 277,000 recorded cases in total. Thus, the identified city is suited for the study to determine the influence of humanized communication to the compliance of the preventive measures against COVID-19.

Population & Sample

The target population of this study is 277,000. Based on the Statista report, as of May 2023, Quezon City has the leading cases of COVID-19 in the National Capital

Region at 277,000 recorded cases, followed by Cavite at 243,000. Using purposive sampling, this study had a sample size of 278 at 6% confidence interval. According to Nikolopoulou (2022), Purposive sampling is a “non-probability sampling techniques in which units are selected because they have characteristics that you need in your sample. Thus, researchers use this so called “judgmental sampling” by identifying and selecting the individuals that can provide the best information for the purpose of the study. Lastly, to make the most out of limited resources, purposive sampling is used. For this research's requirement, respondents must be a Quezon City resident and at least 18 years old.

Research Instrument and Data Collection

To describe the impact and determine the significance of humanizing communication in influencing preventive measures compliance against COVID-19, the respondents were exposed to an advertisement campaign material by P&G Philippines chosen by the researcher entitled, “The Frontliner’s Sacrifice” before answering the questionnaire. The researcher selected the ad campaign based on the following criteria a humanized communication has: (1) STORYTELLING, (2) EMOTIONAL appeal, (3) EMPATHY, (4) INSPIRING TO MOVE TO ACTION. The said ad campaign has 227,000 views and counting on YouTube alone and was released by P&G Philippines in 2020, during the peak of COVID-19 alongside with the strict lockdown implemented nationwide.

The constructs on the questionnaire were borrowed from previous literature to ensure its validity and reworded to specifically relate to the use of humanized communication.

A separate link for the said video was sent to the respondents following the link for the survey questionnaire. Respondents were asked to watch the video before answering the questionnaire.

The survey questionnaire translated in Filipino language was distributed online through Facebook Messenger to selected adult Quezon City residents ages 18 and above. This was composed of four parts: 1) taps emotion; 2) evokes empathy; 3) inspires action; 4) compliance. A coding sheet was set.

The researcher asked for help from peers, colleagues, and students to identify respondents that meet the study's requirements.

A total of 278 responses were received. The margin of error for this sample size is 6% in relation to the total of 227,000 recorded COVID-19 cases in Quezon city as of May 2023. The researcher together with peers, colleagues and students started to collect data through online survey questionnaires using Microsoft Forms last June 9, 2023- June 14, 2023.

Thereafter, respondents were provided with a letter of consent to ensure their anonymity and ensure the confidentiality of their data in compliance to data privacy law.

Data Analysis & Procedure

For this study's purpose, the following methods described the preparation of the collected data for analysis and to provide the rationale in testing the hypothesis.

Initial data collection was digitally conducted by using Microsoft Form. The survey data were then extracted to a Microsoft Excel file for subsequent data analysis.

To measure the association between the factors of humanized communication and preventive measure's compliance against COVID-19 among QC residents, the Spearman's rank correlation test was used. The Spearman's rank correlation test is a non-parametric test that computes a correlation coefficient, rho, to measure the association or correlation of two variables and a test statistic or p-value to assess the significance of the association. For this reason, there are three tests performed, one for each factor of humanized communication with the values on compliance to preventive measures, i.e. (1) Taps Emotion and Compliance; (2) Evokes Empathy and Compliance, and; (3) Inspires Action and Compliance. The calculations were done using the cor test () function, one of the base functions of R software.

Reliability and Validity

For this study, the questionnaire's internal consistency reliability was measured by using Cronbach's alpha value for each construct. All the constructs in the study are deemed acceptable according to Tavakol & Dennick (2011). They reported that a satisfactory alpha score is between 70% to 90%.

Table 1. *Cronbach's alpha values and interpretation for each construct*

Construct	Alpha	Interpretation
Taps Emotion	87.6%	Acceptable
Evokes Empathy	73.5%	Acceptable
Inspires Action	80.1%	Acceptable
Compliance	83.2%	Acceptable

CHAPTER IV

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The researcher received a total of 278 responses from June 9, 2023 to June 14, 2023. The margin of error for this sample size is 6% in relation to the 277,000 recorded COVID-19 cases in Quezon City from the onset of pandemic in 2020 up to May 2023 (Statista, 2023) when the survey was conducted. All of the respondents are currently living in Quezon City, ages 18-years old and above.

Humanized Communication Evoking Emotion

Evoking Emotion by Eliciting Interest

Results showed that the campaign material entitled “The Frontliner’s Sacrifices” was able to educe interest of the respondents (80.6%) as they effectively emphasized through storytelling the daily struggles and sacrifices of our frontliners and (64%) strongly agreed that the ad campaign is effective in getting their interest to adopt the common preventive measures to avoid spreading COVID-19 such as social distancing, isolation, wearing of facemask, and vaccination.

This may also be because many of the respondents (72.7%) strongly agreed that the material was able to convey the message that by adopting the said health protocols, it will mean saving lives of everyone, especially our loved ones.

Also, respondents strongly agreed (77.7%) that the frontliners’ fate and their families rely on their compliance. The findings of the study supported Daradirek Ekachai & James Pokrywczynski (2020) where it was noted that many of the ads created during the peak of COVID-19 employed narrative message strategy that is

related to storytelling to transport and persuade viewers in crafting their public messages. The study showed that it was effectively getting the people’s attention for health and safety purposes.

Table 2. *Humanized communication tapping the interest of the respondents*

STATEMENT	FREQUENCY	ADJECTIVAL RATING
1. The campaign advertisement against COVID-19 educe interest because the way it tells story about the frontliner's struggles and sacrifices was highly emphasized.	224 (80.6%)	Strongly Agree
2. The campaign advertisement is effective in getting the audience interest to adopt the common preventive measures to avoid spreading COVID-19 such as Social distancing, Isolation, Wearing of face mask, Vaccination.	178 (64%)	Strongly Agree
3. The video captures your interest as it was able to convey a message that by adopting the health protocols to prevent the spread of COVID-19 will mean saving lives of everyone, especially our very own family and loved ones.	202 (72.7%)	Strongly Agree
4. The video captures your interest because the frontliners' fate and their families relies as well in your compliance to the health protocols.	216 (77.7%)	Strongly Agree

Note: Strongly agree (5); Agree (4); neutral (3); disagree (2); strongly disagree (1)

In summary, the respondents strongly agreed that humanized communication material that draws interest or attention positively affects their attitude in compliance to the COVID-19 preventive measures. Hence, the material is interesting enough to get the message across.

Evoking Emotion by being Memorable

Respondents strongly agreed (81.3%) that the ad campaign was able to provide vivid image about our frontliners' struggles and sacrifices just to perform their duties. Many of the respondents (70.9%) strongly agreed that even without words pertaining to the health protocols to prevent the spread of COVID-19, the message was effectively conveyed. Seeing scenarios like needing to be away from their families and loved ones gave enough motivation to our respondents (76.3%) to do their part to prevent the spread of COVID-19.

This might also be because our respondents strongly agreed (74.5%) that the ad campaign's emphasis on the daily hardships of our frontliners was an effective reminder to them about the importance of observing the health protocols against COVID-19. This finding backed the study of Nan et al. (2021), where the study recommended that if our goal is to change attitudes and motivate behavior change, COVID-19 messages should use stories. As an example, "COVID-19 messages could feature stories of individuals and families whose lives have been negatively impacted by COVID-19 as a way to encourage risk-reduction behaviors."

Table 3. *Humanized communication by being memorable to respondents*

STATEMENT	FREQUENCY	ADJECTIVAL RATING
1. The ad campaign provides vivid image of frontliners' struggles and sacrifices just to perform their duties.	226 (81.3%)	Strongly Agree
2. Through showing real-life stories of frontliners such as needing to be away with their families and loved ones motivates you to do your part to prevent the spread of COVID-19.	212 (76.3%)	Strongly Agree
3. The frontliners' stories of sacrifices and hardships reminds you of the importance of observing the health protocols against COVID-19.	207 (74.5%)	Strongly Agree
4. Even without words pertaining to the health protocols to prevent the spread of COVID-19, the message was effectively conveyed by vivid stories of our frontliners daily struggles and sacrifices.	197 (70.9%)	Strongly Agree

Note: Strongly agree (5); Agree (4); neutral (3); disagree (2); strongly disagree (1)

In summary, the respondents agreed that providing vivid images and stories of our frontliners' hardships and sacrifices makes it memorable enough to influence them to adopt the preventive measures against COVID-19. Hence, they strongly agreed that it was able to convey the importance of their compliance and cooperation just by showing real-life scenarios of our frontliners.

Humanized Communication Eliciting Empathy

The respondents (79.5%) were able to develop empathy by seeing the real-life stories of our frontliners. They strongly agreed that it helped them realize how they will benefit from observing the health protocols. While 71.9% strongly agreed that the ad campaign was even more compelling as it was able to show the difference of the sacrifices of our frontliners as compared to the majority of Filipinos who were asked to stay at home during lockdowns.

These influenced many of the respondents (69.8%), who recommended seeing more videos like this as they strongly agreed that it is effective in understanding the situation about COVID-19. This is consistent in the study of Kang & Hubbard (2020) and Nan et al. (2021) explaining why narrative messages are more persuasive than non-narrative messages. “Transporting to the narrative world (i.e., being absorbed in the story) and identification with narrative characters (i.e., empathizing with the characters) reduce resistance to persuasion.” Furthermore, people easily feel empathy toward the main characters in the given situation of the plot.

Table 4. *Humanized communication eliciting empathy to our respondents*

STATEMENT	FREQUENCY	ADJECTIVAL RATING
1. The real-life stories of our frontliners shown in the ad campaign helped you realized how will you and your loved ones will benefit from observing health protocols against COVID-19.	221 (79.5%)	Strongly Agree

2. The ad campaign is even more compelling as it was able to show realities of life during this pandemic to those who need to be in frontline such as nurses, doctors, medical personnel, police authorities, delivery riders, etc, as compared to the majority of Filipinos who stay at home during the lockdowns. 200 (71.9%) Strongly Agree

3. For you, would you like to recommend to see more videos like this because you find it effective in understanding the situation about COVID-19? 194 (69.8%) Strongly Agree

Note: Strongly agree (5); Agree (4); neutral (3); disagree (2); strongly disagree (1)

In summary, the respondents strongly agreed that the ad campaign material is compelling enough to develop empathy by showing real-life stories of our frontliners. Hence, the ad campaign's approach is effective in making the audience understand the serious impact of COVID-19 situation by developing empathy.

Humanized Communication Inspiring Action

Results showed that respondents (74.8%) were extremely likely to observe the health protocols against COVID-19 after seeing the frontliners' stories of sacrifices. After seeing how COVID-19 seriously affects the lives of every frontliners, 75.2% of the respondents are extremely likely to comply with the health protocols to further prevent the spread of the virus. Furthermore, they (64.7%) were extremely likely to cooperate and comply with the health protocols upon realizing that stories of sacrifices of our frontliners mirror the repercussions of other people's action when one disregards health protocols. This gave them enough reason to cooperate and comply.

This finding is consistent with the study of Shen et al. (2015), that narrative messages play a vital role in health communication campaigns. The study suggests that “narratives can be influential in changing attitudes, intentions, and behaviors. Narratives can also be effective when the content focuses on the detection and prevention of diseases.”

In terms of the shareability of the ad campaign, the results showed that many of the respondents (63.7%) are extremely likely to share ad campaigns with stories like this that feature the real-life stories of our frontliners to help spread awareness in preventing the spread of COVID-19. This is consistent with the findings of Kang and Hubbard (2021), where the study found that truly, emotion played a crucial role in motivating people to talk about ads through word of mouth. Escalas (2006) also noted that “consumers are more likely to be persuaded by affective outcomes rather than by strong arguments from the information provided in an ad.”

Meanwhile, as the majority of the respondents showed their intent to comply after seeing the ad campaign, only 53.6% said that it is extremely likely that other people will realize the need to adopt the health protocols against COVID-19 after watching stories like the ad campaign features. This echoed the result of the study conducted by Kang & Hubbard (2020), which shows that “persuasive messages in a narrative format might be effective with certain types of people. It has been reported that storytelling advertising is more effective for those who prefer to receive information in a story format.”

Table 5. *Humanized communication inspiring action to respondents*

STATEMENT	FREQUENCY	ADJECTIVAL RATING
1. How likely will you observe the health protocols against COVID-19 after seeing the frontliners' stories of sacrifices?	208 (74.8%)	Extremely Likely
2. How likely will you share ad campaigns with stories like this that feature the real-life stories of our frontliners to help spread awareness in preventing the spread of COVID-19?	177 (63.7%)	Extremely Likely
3. How likely do you think other people will realize the need to adopt the health protocols against COVID-19 after watching stories like the ad campaign features?	149 (53.6%)	Extremely Likely
4. How likely will you comply with health protocols against COVID-19 after seeing how COVID-19 seriously affects the lives of every frontliners and their loved ones?	209 (75.2%)	Extremely Likely
5. Emphasizing stories of sacrifices of our frontliners in the ad campaign mirrors the repercussions of other people's actions not observing the health protocols against COVID-19. This gave you enough reason to comply.	180 (64.7%)	Extremely Likely

Note: Strongly agree (5); Agree (4); neutral (3); disagree (2); strongly disagree (1)

In summary, the likelihood to increase the compliance to preventive measures against COVID-19 is extremely high with the use of humanized communication material that features the real-life stories of our frontliners during the pandemic. With such components of the ad campaign, it was able to show the serious impact of the virus to humanity that gave the respondents the motivation to comply and help spread awareness by sharing videos such as “The Frontliner’s Sacrifice.”

Relationship between Humanized Communication and Compliance

The researcher received a total of 281 responses from June 9, 2023 to June 14, 2023. Hence, to eliminate double entry answers from participants, 278 responses were considered usable for the study. The margin of error for this sample size is 6% in relation to the 277,000 total number of positive cases recorded in Quezon city from the year 2020 up to present, May 2023 when the survey was conducted.

To relate the significance of humanized communication to the respondents’ compliance, the median was computed for each of the constructs to create a summary measure for correlation.

To describe the relationship between humanized communication and compliance, the researcher employed the Spearman’s rank correlation test. The function `cor.test()` in R with a spearman method aided the computations.

Table 6. Spearman’s rank correlation test results for humanized communication and compliance using R

Variables	Rho	Interpretation of rho	p-value	Interpretation of p-value
Taps Emotion ~ Compliance	0.67	Moderate correlation	$< 2.2e^{-16}$	Significant
Evokes Empathy ~ Compliance	0.63	Moderate correlation	$< 2.2e^{-16}$	Significant
Inspires Action ~ Compliance	0.58	Moderate correlation	$< 2.2e^{-16}$	Significant

The result showed that there is a significant correlation between each of the variables of humanized communication to increase their compliance. As for the test on Spearman’s rho, tapping the Emotion to influence Compliance showed a moderate correlation with a rho value of 0.67 and a p-value less than $2.2 e^{-16}$. Thus, tapping the Emotion of the audience significantly influenced their intention to comply with the preventive measures against COVID-19.

Furthermore, a moderate correlation occurred for the variable Empathy that influences intention for compliance of the audience with a rho value of 0.63 and a p-value less than $2.2 e^{-16}$. Hence, a humanized communication material that evokes empathy significantly increases the intention for compliance of the respondents.

As a result, the Humanized Communication material inspires action and increases the respondents' intention for compliance. It has a rho value of 0.58 with a moderate correlation to influence the intention for compliance of the audience and a p-value less than $2.2 e^{-16}$.

In summary, the correlation tests proved to be significant. The data collected from this research provided sufficient evidence to conclude that there is a statistically significant correlation between each of the variables of humanized communication and compliance. Thus, the result from Spearman's rho test with positive values indicates a direct correlation between the variables of humanized communication and compliance. According to Dancey & Reidy (2007), the values suggest a moderate correlation. It means that as the humanized communication variable increases, compliance tends to increase as well.

CHAPTER V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

The study explored what humanized communication is and how it could have a significant influence on compliance of selected Quezon City residents to the preventive measures against COVID-19. The objectives of the study were: 1) To define and explore what humanizes communication; 2) To enumerate the factors that humanize communication; 3) To explain how the factors of humanize communication influence preventive measure's compliance against COVID-19 among QC residents.

The humanized communication material chosen was P&G Philippines' advertisement campaign released in 2020 on YouTube (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=239mhJq34Ro&t=5s>). It has 227,000 views and counting on YouTube alone and it was chosen for being one of the most viewed advertisement campaigns among all the ad campaigns by a commercial brand in the Philippines to address COVID-19 in 2020. The material was released during the peak of COVID-19 in the country and during the strict implementation of lockdowns nationwide to prevent further spread of COVID-19 as the roll of COVID-19 vaccination is still limited.

The study used the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) developed by Martin Fishbein and Icek Ajzen in 1975. A survey was conducted through a purposive sampling design with 278 responses used for the analysis. Cronbach's Alpha was

used to measure the reliability of the test for each variable. To describe the relationship between humanized communication and compliance, the Spearman's rank correlation test was used.

Highlights of the study were the following:

Humanized Communication: Memorable Images through Storytelling

Many of the respondents find the HC material effective in getting their interest to adopt the preventive measures against COVID-19.

The participants strongly agreed that the HC material through its storytelling conveyed the message to the audience. It must be noted that the way they executed the story of our frontliners was effective in giving them enough reason to pay attention to the message of the material.

They strongly agreed that the HC material through its storytelling (emphasizing the daily sacrifices of our frontliners) was able to make the respondents realize that the fate of the frontliners and their loved ones relies on their compliance.

Thus, this study showed that the storytelling used by the ad campaign is a humanized communication as it elicits interest of the audience, influencing them to adopt the preventive measures against COVID-19. This supports the study of Daradirek Ekachai & James Pokrywczynski (2020) that using a narrative message strategy that is related to storytelling to transport and persuade viewers in crafting public messages was effective in getting people's attention for health and safety purposes.

Humanized Communication: Memorable Images through Storytelling

The respondents strongly agreed that providing vivid images of the daily struggle of every frontliners is a factor that makes it memorable to them. This positively influenced their motivation to adopt the message of the said material. Seeing the real-life stories of our frontliners such as needing to be away from their families just to perform their duties motivates them (212) or 76.3%, to do their part to prevent the spread of the virus.

The participants strongly agreed that the power of images used in the storytelling even without using text or words was enough to remember the importance of observing the health protocols in preventing the contagious virus.

Thus, this study showed that the storytelling used by the ad campaign is a humanized communication as the message was memorable enough to remind our audience the impact of their compliance to preventive measures against COVID-19. This finding upheld the study of Nan et al. (2021) where the study recommended that if our goal is to change attitudes and motivate behavior change, COVID-19 messages should use stories. Featuring stories of individuals and families whose lives have been negatively impacted by COVID-19 was seen to encourage risk-reduction behaviors.

Humanized Communication: Evoking Empathy through Storytelling

The respondents strongly agreed that the developed empathy to them after seeing the HC material influences their intention to comply with the preventive measures against Covid-19. They were convinced that the storytelling made them realize how they would benefit from observing the preventive measures against COVID-19. They strongly agreed that it gave a compelling reason to them to cooperate

as it was able to show the incomparable sacrifices and struggles of our frontliners just to perform their duties. Hence, many of the participants recommended seeing more videos like this as they found the approach effective in understanding the situation about COVID-19. This is consistent in the study of Kang & Hubbard (2020) and Nan et al. (2021) emphasizing that in using narrative strategy, people easily feel empathy which results in reducing the resistance to persuasion.

Humanized Communication: Inspiring Action through Storytelling

The survey participants strongly agreed that the HC material through its storytelling inspires action to adopt the preventive measures against COVID-19. Thus, many were convinced and compelled to share the material for spreading awareness.

They strongly agreed that seeing the serious effects of COVID-19 to the frontliners' lives that transcends to their loved ones were factors that motivated them to comply. They also believe that it is extremely likely that other people will also realize the same thing they did about the need to adopt the health protocols.

Thus, the result showed that the likelihood of compliance of our respondents to the preventive measures against COVID-19 is extremely high because the storytelling of the ad campaign was persuasive enough for them to adopt the public health protocols against COVID-19. This finding is consistent with the study of Shen et al. (2015), that narrative messages play a vital role in health communication campaigns. The study suggests that "narratives can be influential in changing attitudes, intentions, and behaviors".

Significance of Humanized Communication to Respondent's Compliance

To relate the significance of humanized communication to the respondent's compliance, the median was computed for each of the constructs to create a summary measure of correlation. To describe the relationship between humanized communication and compliance, the researcher employed the Spearman's rank correlation test. The function `cor.test ()` in R with a `spearman` method aided the computations.

The result showed that there is a significant correlation between each element of humanized communication to influence their compliance. Among the three factors (taps emotion, evokes empathy, and inspiring action), the study showed that tapping the emotion to influence Compliance of our respondents had the highest rho value at 0.67. Followed by the element of evoking empathy to influence compliance with rho value at 0.63. Lastly, the element of HC which is inspiring action had the rho value of 0.58. As a result, the correlation tests proved to be significant. According to Dancey & Reidy (2007), the values suggest a moderate correlation, implying that as the humanized communication variable increases, a positive influence on compliance occurs.

CONCLUSION

Findings suggest that the components of humanized communication through storytelling have significant correlation statistically influencing positively the intention to comply with the preventive measures against COVID-19. As the result showed, the elements of humanized communication through storytelling such as being able to evoke emotion, elicit empathy and inspiring action are factors that make humanized communication influence behavior.

The majority of the respondents strongly agreed that the way the ad campaign tells the stories of our frontliners' struggles and sacrifices educated their interest and made them realize that their fate relies on the public's compliance to the health protocols. The collected data showed that seeing these vivid pictures motivated them to do their part to prevent the spread of the contagious COVID-19. They strongly agreed that the real-life stories and incomparable situation of our frontliners during the peak of pandemic compelled them to cooperate. Thus, humanized communication with its driving factors (taps emotion, evokes empathy and inspires action) can move people to action.

However, the Spearman's rank correlation test results for humanized communication and compliance using R showed that among the three variables (taps emotion, evokes empathy, inspires action), inspiring people to action got the lowest Rho value while evoking Emotion had the highest Rho value that influences positively the intention to comply of the respondents. Thereafter, all the numbers or the values suggest a moderate correlation and have significant p-value according to Dancey & Reidy (2007).

The result of this study showed that humanized communication could have a positive impact for effective communication as we aim for social change. Not only because we are facing a health crisis such as COVID-19, but employing narrative strategy in crafting messages to influence the public's behavior suggests that we can further explore how we can improve our communication approach through humanized communication with consideration on how a HC material can further influence the intention of a person to adopt a behavior.

IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

One of the identified goals of science communication is to help people make sense of science and care about science-related issues. Empowering people to make informed decisions about issues rooted in science is necessary and science communicators have acknowledged utilizing “storytelling: the soul of science communication,” a tool of going beyond presenting facts and evidence by creating emotional connections between scientists and public (Joubert, Davis, & Metcalfe, 2019).

As a developing country, revisiting journals and research that concerns the power of narrative strategy in communicating change, specifically, health communication is exceedingly rare in the country. Thus, it is recommended to conduct interviews among different age groups with access to traditional and digital media. Discussion may revolve around an effective approach communicating science through storytelling in the grass roots. Diffusion of innovation theory may be employed to explore the effective process and timing of communicating change through storytelling.

This study using TRA is also valuable to development communication practitioners working in various government agencies that are concerned in information dissemination about COVID-19 such as the Department of Health, Presidential Communications Office, etc. in understanding what drives the audience to influence their intention to adopt change. The findings of this study suggest that humanized communication positively influences the intention to adopt the preventive measures against COVID-19. However, many ad campaigns were designed by corporate businesses, using this strategy to connect to the public in crisis. It is

recommended to practitioners to pilot test and analyze HC materials that addresses not only our problem with COVID-19 health protocols but also with other health issues the public must be aware of such as the stigma about HIV, Vaccination among children, and the like. Symbolic Interactionism theory may adopt as it discusses why humans act toward things, what shapes these perspectives and how human interaction may change or influence an existing belief.

Furthermore, it is also noticeable that only few literatures are available discussing what humanized communication is. The study suggests humanized communication can positively promote change, particularly in health communication. Today, the potential of humanized communication is being noticed gradually. In fact, in the recently concluded Pinoy Media Congress 2023 in Philippines, the theme was “Humanizing Communication and Media”. This means the communication sector has begun recognizing the potential of humanized communication and media for powerful and effective communication. Thus, it is recommended to conduct a qualitative approach of research by conducting an interview in defining and exploring what is humanizing communication for the people. As the nature of communication continues to evolve, effective communication keeps on changing based on the given situation and environment.

In relation to the results of the study, the researcher believed that in employing humanized communication, there are still more factors that must be considered in carefully crafting our communication messages for social change. In addition to that, it also proved that humanized communication that highly evokes emotion and empathy is undeniable, yet inspiring people to action can still be challenging due to other factors like economic, cultural, religion, misinformation, and other issues.

Observing how some families responded to the said health crisis where lockdowns were strictly implemented back in 2020-2021, this resulted in loss of income to many individuals as the operation of several companies were affected by the implementation of lockdown. According to reports, workers from factories, commercial establishments, transportation industry, and the like were severely affected by the said restrictions. As every family needs to feed and sustain its needs, the challenge of restricting their movements when one experiences symptoms of COVID-19 was never an easy decision for them knowing that they need to find ways to provide for their family. We can also recall that requiring the public to wear face masks and face shields has been an issue because it is an additional expense to every household.

Moreover, there are also known "anti-vaxers" who does not believe that COVID vaccines will help achieve herd immunity to prevent the spread of the virus. Proliferation of misinformation, faster than the information coming from the health authorities, is also a serious problem that causes confusion for the public about what to do when one has symptoms of COVID-19 and how to address it at home. These are just some of the issues that may affect people's intention to adopt the behavior.

Thus, the researcher believes that a holistic approach in crafting our communication messages is evident in achieving social change. In our observation, there are surrounding circumstances that may hinder people to move to action, and these factors can be addressed by not just focusing on telling the public what they should do but also by providing them how they can do it, and how we can help them do it.

Humanized communication described in this study can tap the emotion and develop empathy for a person. Thus, it can drive even more people to action if our HC

material provides a holistic solution to the problem. We can start by checking; does the information we disseminate address the root problem of non-compliance? Is it practical? Will it really help them? Have we tried to answer their how's?

As several studies showed, most of our audience today are now sentient and have easy access to information in just a click away. They have many reasons not to listen to what we are going to say and that is another distraction that may add up to the communication challenges we face. However, the essence of humanized communication demonstrated in this study tells us that with the elements that it has to influence the intention of the people to move into action can be an additional arsenal in transforming the lives of our people. Furthermore, being keen observer through immersion is an advantage in understanding the real situation of our fellowmen. Hence, while humanized communication emphasizes the importance of connecting with people, it also signifies the need to understand and consider what reality is telling us in order to communicate effectively for social change, which is the significance of humanized communication.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

Research Ethics

Ethical considerations were followed as much as possible every step of the way.

Before the respondents may proceed to answering the questionnaire, a consent form was provided to all the respondents via Facebook messenger or email, whichever is preferred by the respondents.

The data collected from the respondents was treated confidential and anonymous only for this study. The participant was informed that the data will be disclosed to a statistician for statistical treatment and analysis of the collected data. All the forms submitted will be password protected for data security and shall be kept by the researcher after the customary 3-5 years in storage.

APPENDX B

INFORMED CONSENT

“ALL WE NEED IS LOVE”: THE INFLUENCE OF HUMANIZED COMMUNICATION TO SELECTED ADULT QUEZON CITY RESIDENTS IN ADOPTING PREVENTIVE MEASURES AGAINST COVID-19

This research aims to determine that humanizing communication increases the intention of Quezon city residents to adopt the preventive measures against COVID-19. May you spare us a bit of your precious time to help us find the answer to our study. The researcher hopes that the result of this study can be a point of reference to further strengthen and improve the COVID-19 response of our city, especially, to avoid detrimental impact of a possible surge in the country.

All the information obtained in this study is strictly confidential unless disclosure is required by the law. For security purposes, each answered form is password protected and will be kept in a password protected computer.

Should you withdraw at any time or refuse to participate, it will not affect you in any way. Every potential respondent is free to participate or refuse answering the questionnaire.

By signing this consent form you are agreeing that you read, or it has been read to you, and you fully understand the contents of this document and are willing to take part in this study. By signing this form, you are agreeing that you are 18 years of age or older and are agreeing to participate in this study.

Signature: _____ Date: _____

APPENDIX C

QUESTIONNAIRE

“ALL WE NEED IS LOVE”: THE INFLUENCE OF HUMANIZED COMMUNICATION TO SELECTED ADULT QUEZON CITY RESIDENTS IN ADOPTING PREVENTIVE MEASURES AGAINST COVID-19

CONSENT FORM

This research aims to determine if humanizing communication motivates the Quezon City residents to increase their intention to adopt the preventive measures against COVID-19. May you spare us a bit of your precious time to help us find the answer to our study.

The researcher hopes that the result of this study can be a point of reference to further strengthen and improve the approach in spreading awareness against COVID-19 and most importantly, inspires people to participate in preventing the spread of COVID-19 through adoption of health protocols to lessen the detrimental impact of a possible surge in the country.

In compliance to the data privacy law, all the information obtained in this study is strictly confidential unless disclosure is required by the law. For security purposes, the data collected will be kept in a password protected computer.

Should you withdraw at any time or refuse to participate, it will not affect you in any way. Every potential respondent is free to participate or refuse answering the questionnaire.

By proceeding to the next page, you are agreeing that you read, or it has been read to you, and you fully understand the contents of this document and are willing to take part in this study. By

*answering this form, you are agreeing that you are 18 years of age or older and are agreeing to participate in this study.
Thank you!*

- I understand and willing to participate in answering this form.
- I refuse to participate to answer this form.

Iyo pong natapos panoorin ang advertisement campaign video bago sagutan itong form.

- Oo
- Hindi

Name: _____

Age: _____

Email address (if applicable) : _____

Matapos mapanood ang advertisement campaign video, piliin kung gaano ka kasang-ayon o hindi sa mga sumusunod na pangungusap:

QUESTIONS:	STRONGLY AGREE	AGREE	NEITHER AGREE NOR DISAGREE	DISAGREE	STRONGLY DISAGREE
1. Ang paraan ng pagkukuwento sa Ad campaign ay nakukuha ang attention ng manonood					
2. Ang ad campaign sa paglaban sa COVID-19 ay nakakapukaw ng interes dahil sa paraan ng pagkukuwento na binigyang diin ang pagpapakita ng sakripisyo at paghihirap na dinadanas ng mga frontliners.					
3. Ang ad campaign ay epektibo sa pagkuha ng interes					

ng tao para sumunod sa mga kalimitang paraan para maiwasan ang pagkalat ng COVID-19 katulad ng pagsunod sa Social distancing, pag-isolate, pagsusuot ng facemask, at pagpapabakuna.					
4. Nakuha ang iyong interest ng bidyo dahil ito ay nakapaghatid ng mensahe na sa pagsunod natin sa mga health protocols para mapigilan ang pagkalat ng COVID-19 ay magliligtas ng buhay ng lahat, lalo't higit ng ating sariling pamilya at mga mahal sa buhay.					
5. Napukaw ang iyong interest sa video dahil nakasalalay din ang buhay at kapalaran ng mga frontliners at ng kanilang pamilya sa pagsunod natin sa mga health protocols.					
6. Ang ad campaign ay nagbigay ng malinaw na larawan sa naranasang paghihirap at sakripisyo ng mga frontliners para lang magampanan ang kanilang mga tungkulin.					
7. Sa pagpapakita ng totoong kwento ng buhay ng mga frontliners katulad ng pangangailangang malayo sa pamilya at mahal sa buhay ay nagbigay motibasyon sa iyo upang gawin ang iyong parte upang mapigil ang pagkalat ng sakit na COVID-19.					
8. Ang kwento ng pagsasakripisyo at paghihirap ng mga frontliners ay nagpapaalala sayo ng kahalagahan ng pag-oobserba ng health protocols laban sa COVID-19.					

9. Kahit walang salita patungkol sa health protocols para mapigil ang pagkalat ng COVID-19, ang mensahe ay epektibong naihatid sa pamamagitan ng malinaw na larawan ng kwento patungkol sa pang araw-araw na sakripisyo at hirap ng mga frontliners.					
	EXTREMELY LIKELY	LIKELY	NEUTRAL	UNLIKELY	EXTREMELY UNLIKELY
10. Gaano ang posibilidad na susundin mo ang health protocols laban sa COVID-19 matapos makita ang kwento ng sakripisyo ng ating mga frontliners?					
11. Gaano ang posibilidad na ibabahagi mo ang ad campaign na tulad nito na tumutukoy sa kwento ng totoong buhay ng frontliners para makatulong sa pagpapalaganap ng kamalayan para mapigil ang pagkalat ng COVID-19?					
12. Sa iyong palagay, gaano ang posibilidad na maiisip ng tao ang pangangailangan na sumunod sa health protocols laban sa COVID-19 pagktapos makapanood ng mga kwento gaya ng pinakita sa ad campaign.					
13. Gaano ang posibilidad na ikaw ay sumunod sa health protocols laban sa COVID-19 matapos makita ang malalang epekto nito sa buhay ng mga frontliners at ng kanilang mga mahal sa buhay?					
	STRONGLY AGREE	AGREE	NEITHER AGREE NOR DISAGREE	DISAGREE	STRONGLY DISAGREE
14. Ang pagpapakita ng totoong buhay ng ating frontliners na pinakita sa ad campaign ay nakatulong sayo					

ma-realize paano ka at ang iyong mga mahal sa buhay makikinabang mula sa pagsunod sa mga health protocols laban sa COVID-19.					
15. Ang ad campaign ay higit na nakakahimok dahil ito ay nakapagpakita ng reyalidad ng buhay ng mga frontliners tulad ng mga nurse, doktor, medical personnel, pulis, delivery riders, etc, sa panahon ng pandemic kumpara sa sakripisyo ng majority ng mga Pilipino na kailangan manatili sa bahay habang pinaiiral ang mga lockdown.					
16. Ang pagbibigay diin sa kwento ng sakripisyo ng mga frontliners sa ad campaign video ay sumasalamin sa resulta ng di pagsunod ng iba sa mga health protocols laban sa COVID-19. Ito ay nagbigay sayo ng sapat na dahilan para makiisa at sumunod sa health protocols.					
17. Para sayo, gusto mo ba na irekomendang makakita ng mas maraming katulad nito na video dahil sa iyong palagay, ito ay epektibo na napapaunawa ang sitwasyon tungkol sa COVID-19?					